

Chickpea nodulation in Turkish field soils

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Abstract. With Turkey being the centre of origin of cultivated chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) and the native range of other members of the genus, including the progenitors of *C. arietinum*, its soils are likely to contain an unexplored diversity of chickpea-nodulating rhizobia. The potential advantages of finding and deploying more effective rhizobia strains in commercial chickpea production justify more extensive sampling of Turkish cropping soil. In this study, chickpea nodulation (in greenhouse-grown trap plants) was quantified (with lentil as a comparator) for cropping soils collected in nine provinces across Central Anatolia, Mediterranean and Southeastern Anatolia Regions of Turkey (180 sites). Chickpea and lentil were able to be grown using soil from 173 and 167 sites, respectively; 161 and 158 with nodules. Regression and principal component analyses revealed strong relationships between nodulation and plant growth, and moderate relationships between prior crop and geographical location and nodulation. Most notably, 93% samples contained sufficient compatible rhizobia to nodulate chickpea even though mostly coming from sites/localities where cultivated and wild chickpeas are not commonly grown or growing. This frequency was similar to lentil (95%), which was expected to have a high nodulation frequency given the widespread occurrence of other hosts of lentil-nodulating rhizobia. Isolation of rhizobia from this collection of material is likely to provide diverse genotypes, some of which may be useful as commercial inoculant.

Keywords: biological nitrogen fixation, chickpea, nodulation, pulse crop, rhizobial distribution, rhizobial incidence

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Introduction

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*), the second most important cool-season pulse crop (Merga & Haji 2019), was domesticated in the winter-rainfall zone of West Asia, most likely in what is now southeastern Turkey (Redden & Berger 2007). With global production of over 16 Mt in 2023 (FAO 2025), it is a particularly valued component of diets in India, Pakistan and Turkey, with India being the major global producer (over 12 Mt in 2023). In addition, it is also grown in suitable environments worldwide, with some countries, including Australia (99% exported), Canada and Mexico (DAFF 2023), largely producing chickpea for export. The key advantages of chickpeas, as a food crop, are its environmental tolerance, capacity for biological nitrogen fixation and consequent high protein

content, which, along with other nutritional attributes, makes it a beneficial and affordable protein-rich dietary staple (Millán *et al.* 2015). However, chickpea production is relatively difficult compared to cereals and some other pulses (Anon. 2017a), and there remains a large gap between potential and actual yields in most production environments (Peake *et al.* 2021).

In Turkey, despite being the third largest producer, after India and Australia, chickpea is generally a low-priority dryland crop grown in small fields (mostly <10 ha) with only minimal to moderate inputs, rarely inoculated, with most growers not using certified seeds, and yields only averaging around 1 t/ha (Cakmakci *et al.* 1988; Kahraman 2022; Sakar *et al.* 1988). Consequently, there is likely to be a substantial gap between these

actual yields and what is theoretically achievable, but this does not appear to have been quantified in Turkey. For comparison, in Australia with long-term average yields (20 years to 2015) somewhat lower than Turkey at 0.8 and 1 t/ha in southern and northern regions, respectively, with water-limited yield gaps were estimated at 1.6 to 2.4 t/ha (Peake *et al.* 2021).

In Turkey, as elsewhere, one important strategy to fill the yield gap in chickpea production is to facilitate effective nodulation through inoculation with rhizobia suited to the cultivar and local conditions (Altuntaş *et al.* 2024; Elkoca *et al.* 2015; Gebremariam & Tesfay 2021). Earlier isolation of rhizobia from chickpea grown in Turkey provided effective strains, but at that time inoculation did not significantly improve yields of crops grown in Turkish soils, which are likely to have moderate to high populations of resident (often called "native") rhizobia (Cakmakci *et al.* 1988). Assuming there was no direct cause for inoculation failure, it is likely that the inoculant strains failed to compete with resident, locally-adapted genotypes (Dowling & Broughton 1986), which are expected to occur in these Turkish soils.

The wild progenitors of domesticated chickpeas are relatively rare in southeastern Turkey with specimens of *Cicer echinospermum* or *C. reticulatum* found at only 21 sites during nearly 2 months¹ of searching using local guides (von Wettberg *et al.* 2018). From these species, and *C. arietinum* samples, across 10 sites, 38 strains of four species of chickpea rhizobia were isolated, *Mesorhizobium ciceri* (22 strains), *M. mediterraneum* (8 strains), *M. muleiense* (5 strains) and *M. plurifarium* (3 strains), with all these species also isolated from the cultivated chickpea (Greenlon *et al.* 2019). As in that work and common practice, it appears that chickpea rhizobia have only been obtained in Turkey from nodulated legumes (e.g., Basbuga *et al.* 2021; Cakmakci *et al.* 1988; Küçük & Kivanç 2008; Mahmoud *et al.* 2019). One study assessed resident populations of chickpea-nodulating rhizobia in Turkey with samples from four Turkish provinces (4 samples each) found to be low low (0 to 10²/g soil) but rhizobia were not isolated and characterised (Cakmakci *et al.* 1988). There appears to be no reports of quantification or

isolation of rhizobia from soils where chickpeas (native or cultivated) may not have grown for many years, if ever. Consequently, the existence and composition of resident, chickpea-nodulating rhizobium more widely in Turkey is unknown.

Knowledge of the occurrence and diversity of resident chickpea-nodulating rhizobia in Turkish soil could underpin the search for effective, competitive strains for optimal chickpea production using biologically fixed nitrogen for Turkey and elsewhere. To initiate this, chickpea and lentil (the latter as a comparator species) were grown in soil samples collected from cropped fields in nine Turkish provinces to assess nodulation in relation to current land use and geographic location, and to collect material for subsequent isolation and identification of rhizobia.

Materials and methods

Soil samples

Soil from cropping fields (180 sites) in nine provinces across three regions (Central Anatolia, Mediterranean and Southeastern Anatolia) of Turkey were collected after harvest in the summer of 2021. The crop species (including cabbage, cereal², chickpea and sugarbeet) and geographic coordinates for each site (Fig. 1) were recorded. Sample numbers for province, region and locality are given in Table S1. The relative proportions of prior crops for the nine provinces sampled are shown in Fig. 2. In most provinces, the majority of samples came from cereal fields, except for Konya, where sugarbeet was and remains the predominant crop. Some cabbage fields were sampled in Niğde, and chickpea fields in Nevşehir and Kayseri. Although the sampling team aimed to sample more chickpea fields in all provinces visited, only five were found in the latter two provinces.

Surface soil to 250 mm deep was collected and mixed from about 30 points within each field along a zigzag of three transects each with 10 sampling points (c. 5 m apart) starting about 20 m in from one edge of the field³. The samples were placed in cloth bags and allowed to air dry before storage under laboratory conditions.

¹ The cited source has both 46 and 53 days.

² The cereal sites were in the vast majority wheat, but give sample were taken after harvest, and often after postharvest grazing, it is not possible to exclude the possibility that some were barley.

³ This sampling was originally done with a focus on determining prevalence of certain crop nematodes but also enabled this opportunity to examine in prevalence of chickpea-nodulating rhizobia in these cropping areas with a relatively low frequency of chickpea production.

Fig. 1 Location of cropping fields sampled in nine Turkish provinces: Adana, Gaziantep, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Konya, Nevşehir, Niğde and Osmaniye. Province, region and locality details provided in Table S1.

Fig. 2 Soil samples by prior crop type. Crop types: yellow, chickpea; orange, cereals; pink, sugarbeet; and grey; cabbage. Provinces: Ada, Adana; Gaz, Gaziantep; Hat, Hatay; Kah, Kahramanmaraş; Kay, Kayseri; Kon, Konya; Nev, Nevşehir; Nig, Niğde; and Osm, Osmaniye.

Greenhouse culture of chickpeas and lentils in test soils

Tapered black plastic pots (1.5 L; 115 x 115 x 183 mm; square top with 90 mm circular base) were filled with the test soil (c. 500 g) sandwiched between two layers of washed builder's sand (c. 700 and 350 g lower and upper layers, respectively) that contained sufficient fine materials to allow adequate wetting with bottom watering. One pot containing soil from each collection site was prepared and arbitrarily allocated to four greenhouse benches (c. 300 mm apart) standing in individual containers (120 x 80 x 50 mm; transparent polyethylene terephthalate food containers) for bottom watering. Seeds of chickpea (*C. arietinum* cv. Azkan) were germinated in moist paper towel in the laboratory (c. 25°C), and the seedlings transplanted (17 March 2022, 2/pot, 20 mm deep) into the top layer of sand in the pots in the greenhouse within 1-2 days of radicle emergence (c. 3 days from initial wetting). Seedlings failed to emerge or establish in 8% of pots and these were replaced in early April with only 13 of 30 replacement plants surviving⁴. Subsequently,

⁴ Herbicide residues or soilborne pathogens might have been responsible for the initial and subsequent establishment failures.

lentil⁵ (*Lens culinaris* cv. Koç) was grown for comparative purposes following the same procedure (transplanting on 30 September 2022) with a similar failure rate (7%, no replacements were planted).

Growth medium moisture was maintained throughout the experiment by refilling the bottom-watering containers with untreated artesian water as needed. Care was taken to avoid cross and ambient contamination, including bottom watering and well-spaced pots. Five control pots were included as indicators of possible contamination. These contained heat-treated soil (c. 500 g) from five arbitrarily selected locations, which were pre-moistened, spread on aluminium foil heated to 121°C for 2 h. The experiment was maintained for 2-3 months, being harvested as four batches of 45 (early June for chickpea and late November for lentil).

Assessment of plant growth and nodulation

For chickpea, plant height was recorded during growth (at 2-weekly intervals; 31 March, 15 and 29 April, and 13 and 27 May) and leaf chlorophyll assessed by chlorophyll meter (SPAD-502 Plus, Konica Minolta Optics, Inc., Osaka, Japan) about the week before harvest (26 May). At harvest (for both chickpea and lentil), the plants were removed from the pots, gently washed to remove the growth medium and stored at 2°C (if not processed on that day), and then nodules were picked, counted and air dried⁶ (laboratory conditions, 26-28°C for 72 h) for future isolation. The whole plants (nodules removed) were weighed before and after oven drying (60°C for 48 h).

Data analysis

The data set for analysis included prior crop (in the sampling year), latitude, longitude, elevation, plant chlorophyll, height and dry weight (the former two only for chickpea⁷), and nodule number [$\log_{10}(x + 1)$ transformed]. A single-value per experimental unit plant height variate was derived from the five assessments by fitting the three-parameter function *LL.3()* using the dose response model function *drm()*

of the R package 'drc' (ver. 3.0-1; Ritz *et al.* 2015) then for further analysis using the value predicted for 71 days. Also, with 8% chickpea seedlings replaced about 3 weeks after the original planting, the final heights of these were lower (mean of 265 versus 391 mm) due to delayed establishment and/or competition with an established paired plant (5 pots had both seedlings replaced and 20 pots had a single seedling replaced). In response, an ordinal factor (0, 1 and 2 plants replaced) was included for initial analysis but was found not to provide any particular efficacy for subsequent analysis.

As the categorical variate, prior crop, was not well distributed spatially and was dominated by cereals, it was only visualised against province but was used for statistical analysis against nodule number. This was done with R (version 4.4.2; R Core Team 2024) by plotting an *xtabs()* contingency table in the R package "stats" for prior crop by province, and by linear regression with a categorical factor using R package "visreg" (Breheny and Burchett 2017). All combinations of the continuous variates were likewise initially examined by linear regression using "visreg" with and without several data transformations (\log_{10} , and cubic and quartic roots). Means were compared by least significant difference. The best fits were then included in a principal component analysis using *procomp()* of the R package "stats" followed by visualisation of the biplot, scree plot and correlation matrix, the latter using R package "corrplot" (Wei and Simko 2024).

Results

Chickpea

Chickpea plants were successfully grown and assessed for 173 of the 180 soil samples⁸. Nodules were produced in 161 (93%) of the 173 pots in which plants grew (positives by locality are given in Table S1). By province, this proportion ranged from 71 to 100% with four provinces below 100%; Niğde, Konya, Kayseri and Hatay at 71, 84, 85 and 90%, respectively. With nodule counts ranging up to 262 per plant, this variate was highly skewed and was log transformed for all analyses.

⁵ Lentil was selected as a comparator because it is nodulated by *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *viciae* as with other species in Fabaeae tribe, with the vetches being both widespread and species rich in Turkey (Adigüzel *et al.* 2010; Basbag 2013). Therefore it is reasonable to expect it to be ubiquitous in Turkish cropping soils.

⁶ Although weights were taken the material was not uniformly dry to constant weight at that time, so these weights have not been included here or used in the analysis.

⁷ Plant chlorophyll and height data were not found to particularly informative and, not being available for lentil, these were not included in the results presented.

⁸ Those in which establishment failed probably contained herbicide residues toxic to chickpea.

The five chickpea sites gave the highest median nodule number per plant (54 per pot, back-transformed), followed by cereal (29), sugarbeet (7) and cabbage (2) for 145, 18 and 5 sites, respectively (Fig. 3A). Nodule numbers for chickpea and cereal sites were not significantly different (with many cereal sites given nodule numbers in excess of the median for chickpea sites falling fully within the range of nodule numbers obtained from wheat sites

maximum numbers being obtain from cereal sites; Fig. 3A). The nodule numbers for sugarbeet and cabbage sites were significantly lower than for the cereal sites and differed from each other ($p < 0.01$; Table S3). Nodules were obtained for the five chickpea sites, however, nodules were not obtained from eight cereal (5%), three (19%) sugarbeet and two cabbage (22%) sites. The heat-treated controls were mostly unnodulated (Table S2), except for a

Fig. 3 Chickpea nodule numbers per plant (log transformed): A, by crop type (with blue line being median and grey rectangles the interquartile range); B, versus shoot weight; C, versus latitude; and D, versus longitude (with the blue lines the linear fit and the grey area the 95% confidence band). Crop types: yellow, chickpea; orange, cereals; pink, sugarbeet; and grey, cabbage. Provinces: Ada, Adana; Gaz, Gaziantep; Hat, Hatay, Kah, Kahramanmaraş; Kay, Kayseri; Kon, Konya; Nev, Nevşehir; Nig, Niğde; and Osm, Osmaniye. Statistical is analysis provided in Table S3.

Fig. 4 Lentil nodule numbers per plant (log transformed): A, by crop type (with blue line being median and grey rectangles the interquartile range); B, versus shoot weight; C, versus latitude; and D, versus longitude (with the blue lines the linear fit and the grey area the 95% confidence band). Crop types: yellow, chickpea; orange, cereals; pink, sugarbeet; and grey, cabbage. Provinces: Ada, Adana; Gaz, Gaziantep; Hat, Hatay, Kah, Kahramanmaraş; Kay, Kayseri; Kon, Konya; Nev, Nevşehir; Niğ, Niğde; and Osm, Osmaniye. Statistical analysis is provided in Table S3.

single or a few small, white nodules from two of the treated soils⁹. There was no evidence of contamination from the substrate used or the greenhouse environment.

Regression analysis revealed a range of clear relationships within and between the geographic,

plant and nodule variates. The most informative of these, nodule weight versus shoot weight, latitude and longitude are shown here (Fig. 3). With plant weight (Fig. 3B), there was a moderately strong positive association (accounting for c. 44% of the variation; Table S3). There were some sites with the

⁹ In these instances, the treatment must not have been fully effective given the high resident populations in these samples, which was indicated by large numbers of nodules in the untreated test.

Fig. 5 Distribution of chickpea and lentil nodule numbers per plant (as raw means). The horizontal blue line is the mean and the black line the median.

plant response well above the main trend line, potentially indicative of rhizobial populations being atypically more effective in chickpea than the majority. However, with no nitrogen-free basal fertiliser provided, variation in plant growth response could be driven by both efficacy of nodulation and the nutritional status of the test soil. For latitude and longitude (Fig. 3C,D), there were negative and positive relationships, respectively, explaining 9% and 25% of the variation (Table S3) indicating a moderate increasing trend in nodule number from W to E but only a minimal S to N response.

Lentil

For the lentil comparator, the results were similar. Plants were successfully grown and assessed for 167 samples with nodules were produced in 158 pots (95%) (Table S1). By province, this proportion ranged from 85 to 100% with five provinces below 100%; Kayseri, Niğde, Konya, Nevşehir and Osmaniye at 84, 85, 94, 94 and 95%, respectively; values that are only marginally greater than for chickpea. With nodule counts ranging up to 115 per plant, as with chickpea, this variate was highly skewed and was log transformed for all analyses.

Similar to chickpea, the five chickpea sites gave the highest median nodule number per plant (27 per pot, back-transformed), followed by cereal (11), sugarbeet (4) and cabbage (2) at 137, 18 and 6 sites, respectively (Fig. 4A). In contrast to chickpea, the

nodule numbers for each prior crop were all significantly different (in decreasing order): chickpea, cereal, sugarbeet and cabbage (with p-values ranging from 0.05 to 0.001; Table S3). Nodules were obtained for all chickpea sites, however, nodules were not obtained from 15 wheat (10%), four (20%) sugarbeet and two cabbage (22%) sites. The lentil controls had 0 to 3.5 nodules per plant (Table S2), except the Adana sample for which the heat treatment was not fully effective. Despite this, the nodule numbers in the controls were well below their untreated equivalents, and there was no evidence of any confounding contamination from the substrate used or the greenhouse environment.

Combined chickpea and lentil

A comparison of the distribution on nodule numbers per plant is given in Fig. 5 as raw numbers (not back-transformed as above). The median nodule number were 35 for chickpea and 21 for lentil. As an aggregative method, responses for all variates for chickpea and lentil, analysed by PCR and examined through a correlation matrix, are given in Fig. 6. The first and second principal components explained nearly 65% of the variation (Fig. 6A) indicating the robustness of the PCA undertaken. The four plant and nodule variates were aligned (codependent) with the two for chickpea most clearly codependent. The chickpea variates were largely independent (i.e., vectors nearly perpendicular) to the three geographic variates (Fig. 6B). For the latter, the three variates were co-dependant, with longitude negatively so. However, the lentil variates, weaker in the overall contribution (shorter vector length), tended to be more aligned with longitude. These multivariate relationships are reflected well in the correlation matrix (Fig. 6C).

In the correlation matrix (Fig. 6C), the strongest relationship was between elevation and latitude ($R = 0.83$), which merely reflects the fact that the more easterly provinces sampled (Adana through to Gaziantep) have lower altitudes lower than those on the Anatolian Plateau (Konya to Niğde). The clustering of the points into two diagonal clusters within the PCR biplot (Fig. 6B) is driven by this geography as samples were not collected in the intervening Anti-Taurus (Aladağlar) Mountains. This geography had only a moderate impact on plant and nodule variates, with the largest (though still relatively weak) response being longitude versus lentil nodule number ($R = 0.46$) as plotted in Fig. 4C. For the plant variates, there was a predictable association between weight and nodule number (chickpea $R = 0.60$ and lentil $R = 0.53$).

Fig. 6 A, Principal component scree plot for chickpea and lentil variates; B, biplot of the first two PCs; and C, correlation matrix for variates represented in A and B. The colours in the correlation matrix ranging from dark red to dark blue represent the strength of the association from $R = -1$ to 1 .

Discussion

The main finding of this investigation was the widespread and high incidence of chickpea-nodulating rhizobia in the nine provinces of Turkey sampled. This was commensurate with the lentil comparator, and included sites and areas where recent growth of chickpea (at the site or nearby) would have been unlikely. In the sampled part of Turkey, without targeted sampling based on local advice, only a small number of chickpea fields were found. Only two of the provinces sampled, Kayseri

and Konya, are in the top ten chickpea growing provinces of Turkey (Burucu 2024), with chickpea area representing only 2.4 and 1.2% of the provincial cropped area, respectively. As a relatively minor crop, chickpea fields are likely to have a non-uniform distribution, so the non-targeted sampling undertaken predictably missed these fields. Likewise, as explained above from the work of von Wettberg *et al.* (2018), wild chickpea species would also be difficult to find. This means that the rhizobia with the chickpea symbiotic island (Muleta *et al.*

2022) are effectively surviving as free-living organisms in these agricultural soils, which is not an intuitively predictable outcome. In subsequent work (unpublished data; ITR and coworkers) isolates from these nodules were determined by molecular methods to include *M. ciceri*, *M. loti*, *M. mediterraneum* and *M. muliense*, so the chickpea symbiotic island was not rhizobial-species-specific in the sampled area, which could possibly have resulted from horizontal transfer (Zaw *et al.* 2021; Muleta *et al.* 2022).

It is therefore likely that the rhizobial genotypes responsible for the nodulation observed in this study are well adapted to local climatic and edaphic conditions. Consequently, these genotypes are (1) likely to be competitive with any inoculant strain applied, and (2) not particularly symbiotically effective (Triplett and Sadowsky 1992; Greenlon *et al.* 2019; Rathjen *et al.* 2024). In both cases, this would present challenges for successful inoculation as well as finding improved strains to achieve this. Nevertheless, the variation in plant growth response (dry weight) as a function of nodule weight (Fig. 3B) shows that in some instances the symbiotic performance could have potentially been superior. Even though these data were collected from single replicates (with up to 2 plants), it is sufficient to assume the merit of isolation and further evaluation rhizobium from chickpea nodules obtained in this way. Putatively useful rhizobial strains have been isolated from nodules of a wild species, *Cicer anatolicum*, occurring in the highlands of Erzurum, Eastern Anatolia (Ögütçü *et al.* 2008). Further assessment of the material collected in this study and further collections from soil in atypical contexts through host-baiting could prove productive in finding effective strains that are competitive with genotypes resident in soils in Turkey or even superior to the commercial inoculant strains used in countries like Australia.

Notwithstanding the value of this research as detailed above, the data collected on per plant nodule numbers appears inconsistent with expectations. Generally, nodule numbers for chickpea are low compared to lentil, with adequate nodulation ranges under Australian conditions deemed to be 10-30 for chickpea and 50-100+ for lentil (Anon. 2017b; Farquharson *et al.* 2022). However, in recent greenhouse experiments conducted with some Turkish isolates obtained from this collection, nodule numbers ranged up to 50 per plant (unpublished data; ITR and coworkers). In the wider literature, numbers for chickpea can be even higher, reaching over 100 per plant (Biabani *et al.* 2011; for others see Table S4). In the present study, the medium nodule numbers for chickpea was 35 (Fig. 5), which is not inconsistent with the literature

even though 32 responses exceed 100. The reason for is likely to be the nature of the nodulating rhizobia present in the samples and the assay system used. Most chickpea nodulation data in the literature is for plants inoculated with *M. ciceri* cultures not for more genetically/species diverse populations of resident chickpea-nodulating rhizobia surviving saprophytically for extended periods. Also, in the assay system used, the plant roots had to grow through a moderate depth of inert substrate before reaching the layer of field soil, and late nodulation of ramifying roots is likely to result in greater nodule numbers, just as it can with symbiotically inefficient genotypes. Nevertheless, it is evident that field soils assayed in this way is likely to access rhizobial genotypes that might not readily be obtained by the common approach of isolating from nodulated legumes or soils in pulse production contexts.

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Supplementary information

Supplementary information and analyses are available for download at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19433992>.

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